

D4.1: Multi-sectorial trends and drivers shaping the future of European transport

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report focuses on the initial steps of the REBALANCE scenario building process and the main results achieved.

Chapter 1 sets the scene for the REBALANCE scenario building and highlights its innovative features.

Chapter 2 describes the horizon scanning carried out to identify an initial list of trends and signals that are deemed relevant for the specific scope of REBALANCE, i.e. key factors that point at possible changes in mobility culture and the underlying values. 30 trends and signals were thus identified, addressing the main dimensions of the mobility debate: lifestyles, travel habits, modal choices, vehicles and systems, city visions, social interactions.

Chapter 3 provides a detailed account of a series of exploratory conversations that were staged with thinkers and experts in order to complement and sharpen the initial list of trends and drivers. It presents 20 additional trends/signals, with a distinctive focus on cultural and value-based dynamics.

Chapter 4 explains how the consolidated list of drivers resulting from the previous steps was re-elaborated to devise a final list of drivers and better characterise their relevance to mobility culture. A final selection of 12 drivers is thus proposed.

Chapter 5 outlines the way forward, including a review and validation of the selected drivers and the identification of a short list of Critical Uncertainties, to feed into the design of the REBALANCE scenario space.

2 INTRODUCTION

REBALANCE is an open deliberative forward-looking exercise aiming at conception and validation of a new transport paradigm reflecting a new mobility culture. The exercise pushes for a more effective ponderation of the emerging social values not yet fully considered in transport policymaking, and a better alignment with the SDGs and the mounting concerns about climate change.

REBALANCE moves from the assumption that the mobility culture that currently prevails in the world (including Europe) has led to unsustainable travel patterns, in social and environmental terms. From a critical review of the present (see deliverables D3.2 and D3.3) also in the light of the recent COV19 pandemic, REBALANCE is building a vision over the future and a roadmap to achieve it, which will be embedded in a Manifesto with the aim to stimulate European policymakers to adapt concrete legal and political measures while moving the wider European communities towards a radical change.

This Deliverable reports on the initial steps of the REBALANCE scenario building process. Figure 1 shows the overall sequence of this process, which - in line with the mainstream foresight methodologies - starts with horizon scanning and ends with the narratives of the REBALANCE scenarios. D4.1 deals with the first three steps.

Figure 1 - The scenario building process

A variety of foresight studies have been carried out in recent years to explore the future dynamics of transport and mobility¹, including the on-going EEA study on urban mobility at 2050². Many of these projects focus primarily on the future of technologies, or on specific transport sectors. The original focus of REBALANCE, on the other hand, entails a novel and deeper attention to the cultural and value-based factors that play a role in collective and individual mobility choices and orientations, notably including modal

¹ See for instance:

[Home - Intend Project \(intend-project.eu\)](https://intend-project.eu)
<file:///C:/Users/ADMINI~1/AppData/Local/Temp/Future-Transport-UK.pdf>
https://www.izt.de/en/topics/view/project/global_foresight_transport_under2/
<https://www.mobility4eu.eu/>
<https://www.adlittle.com/en/insights/report/future-mobility-post-covid>
<http://www.mind-sets.eu/>
<https://home.kpmg/uk/en/home/campaigns/2019/09/mobility-2030-future-of-mobility.html>
<https://www.waterborne.eu/projects/coordination-projects/steerer/>

² 'European urban mobility 2050: A horizon scanning project' - Foresight on Demand consortium

choices and travel behaviours on the demand side, and the planning of infrastructure and innovative services on the supply side.

This has prompted the development of an additional step, to bridge the “traditional” exploration of trends and weak signals that drive mobility choices with the identification of cultural and value-based factors that reflect the deeper roots behind such trends and signals.

Accordingly, the critical uncertainties that will be prioritised in the next steps - when devising a meaningful framework for scenario building - will be selected among drivers that explicitly point to basic values and cultural tenets behind mobility choices and orientations.

The following chapters describe in more detail the methodological approach adopted for each step and the main findings.

3 OVERVIEW OF TRENDS AND WEAK SIGNALS

The scanned sources include:

- Recent literature on transport and mobility trends (studies, policy briefs)
- Press and media articles
- Statements from experts and opinion leaders

A list of the main references is provided in **Annex 1**.

Although most of the trends and signals emerging from the scanning (ca. 200) could ultimately bear some degree of relevance for cultural and value-based dynamics, a shorter set of 30 items was then extracted, for which the cultural and value-based relevance is considered both direct and highly challenging.

Table 1 below presents the selected trends and weak signals. Many of these originate in the transport and mobility sector itself, while others illustrate dynamics that are likely to affect mobility choices but reflect broader phenomena. Trends/signals are grouped in 6 main categories, each corresponding to a basic dimension of the mobility culture:

- ✓ Lifestyles
- ✓ Travel habits
- ✓ Modal choices
- ✓ Vehicles and systems

- ✓ The vision of the city
- ✓ Social interactions

These dimensions are not meant to serve as a definite taxonomy of trends and signals, but rather to help organizing and characterizing them and ensuring that a balanced variety/diversity is achieved

In addition to the short description provided for each item, the table classifies them according to the well-known PESTLE framework (Figure 2 below).

Figure 2 - The PESTLE approach

Trends/signals are shown with a “dominant” PESTLE dimension (capital X), along with “secondary” ones (lower case x), reflecting the often complex interplay between e.g. policy and economy, technology and environment etc. Overall, the PESTLE coverage is consistent with the overall focus of REBALANCE, with the Social dimension strongly represented, followed by the Policy and Legal dimensions.

TABLE1: Trends and Signals from literature review, press and media

Dimension	Trends and Signals	Description	P	E	S	T	L	E
Lifestyles	Urban exodus, younger generations get away from cities	In addition to an uncontroversial trend towards increasing urbanization on all continents, there is also a movement back to less urban areas. Driven by the pressure of housing costs and a surge in homeworking stemming from the COVID-19 pandemic, urban dwellers (especially the younger generations) are rediscovering the benefits of rural and small town living as an alternative to the stresses and strains of the modern urban world.		x	X			
	Polytopic living is accelerating	Polytopic living and intensive mobility are societal changes that started a long time ago but now are notably accelerating. an increasing number of people have two or more residences due to divorce and joint custody of children, by choice, for work-related or for leisure-related reasons, which intensifies movements to and from their living places	X		x			
	Flexible remote work is on the rise	As accentuated by the pressure to work from home because of COVID-19, employers as well as employees have gained experience from remote work and will seek for new arrangements to organize work. There will be more flexibility to work from home or office hotels, to combine (personal) travel and work, etc., and needs for traditional offices and traditional commuting will diminish.		X	x		x	
	Business and lack of leisure time become a status symbol	Being busy, living a hectic life conveys the idea that you are indispensable to society				X		
	Consumption and shopping patterns are in continuous evolution	Anything, Anytime, Anywhere – Consumers strive for convenient solutions in all aspects of their lives. On-line shopping is on the rise, further boosted by the general lockdowns during the COVID pandemic. These changes in consumer behavior will influence all the actors in the value chain, including transportation .		x	X			
	Increasing awareness of the environmental impact of transport influences decisions of customers to buy locally	Consumers are becoming more aware of the environmental footprint of transport which is reflected in a change of their consumption habits. The tendency to buy local is a recent phenomenon, which became much stronger with the COVID pandemic. As a result, people tend to rely less on global trade, preferring to pay more for clean local products and services. 'Localism' is forecast to be a major post-pandemic trend, which might lead to changes or even disruptions in supply chains in the future.		x	X			
Travel habits	Reductions in daily mobility and long-distance domestic travel are observed among the young	The increased 'virtualization', which is very marked among young people, and there are some indications that increasing Internet use among young adults is associated with less travel. Another aspect is the gradual lengthening of the post-adolescent period that is often associated with limited economic resources potentially restricting travel. However, this development also implies the postponement of professional and familial obligations, generally				X		

Dimension	Trends and Signals	Description	P	E	S	T	L	E
		meaning less strict time–spatial constraints, potentially promoting the long-distance mobility of young adults						
	Leisure travel remains high-carbon	Key drivers for mass tourism will remain money, time and technology. Even those people who regularly consume or behave in an environmentally friendly fashion — whether it's what they buy, whether they recycle or whatever it might be — research has found that they actually temporarily forget their environmental credentials, and behave like normal tourists. They do suffer some kind of ecoguilt, but nevertheless they continue to travel, they continue to fly.			X			x
	Leisure travel is booming after the pandemic	As the worst effects of the COVID-19 pandemic ebb, most indicators point to travel coming back—with a vengeance—as people look to reconnect, explore new destinations, or revisit reliable favorites. Many just want to get away from the confines of their homes. A McKinsey survey reveals traveling to be the second-most-desired activity among respondents (in first place: dining out).	x	X				
	Business travel is in structural decline	Companies are expected to keep a tight rein on trips in the coming years, leading to a “structural” decline of between 15% and 25% through 2025 from before the Covid-19 pandemic. There will be a long-lasting effect from hybrid working and reduced corporate spending on travel. For the lucrative business-travel segment, the biggest threat comes from cutbacks in internal meetings — which make up roughly 40% of corporate travel — while trips to meet customers are more likely to be maintained.		X	x			
Modal choices	Usage of bikes as means of transport is growing significantly due to the pandemic	Cycling is gaining momentum in many cities around the world as people are increasingly looking for greener, healthier modes of transport. Cycle-friendly cities such as Paris, Amsterdam and Copenhagen continue to invest in their bike-sharing schemes and the expansion and improvement of their already extensive cycling networks. Sustainable means of transport will overtake car usage over the next decade, with public transport, cycling and walking representing a total of 49% of all trips undertaken within cities versus 46% for cars. Cycling is predicted to enjoy the largest increase as number of car trips decrease. Covid-19 brought about a dramatic increase in bicycle sales in response to the pandemic. Heightened anxiety over public transportation and a surge in exercise has meant that more and more are choosing to use one of the most basic forms of mobility, leading to a so-called “bike boom”.			X			

Dimension	Trends and Signals	Description	P	E	S	T	L	E
	People is expected to use (e)scooters more frequently	<p>Scooter users are spending more time on the vehicles than they were before the pandemic hit. Tier has seen a 20 per cent global increase in ride duration, trips taken on Voi's scooters are almost double as long as pre-Covid (now 18 minutes on average), while Lime says it's seeing rides in Europe that are 25 per cent longer on average. Scooter companies are also reporting more journeys starting and ending in residential areas. This — along with the longer ride times — suggests that scooters are being used more for utility than for sightseeing at the moment. A survey by LIME, an electric scooter company, found that a higher share of people in cities including Berlin, London and Seoul say they expect to use e-scooters more frequently than before the virus.</p>			X	x		
	The use of public transportation is declining due to the pandemic	<p>Concerns over infection makes people uneasy about using public transport - even after the world emerges from the coronavirus pandemic, say experts. This means that private car use could rise, leaving public transportation agencies again fighting against falling ridership – and increasing the risk that pollution and congestion remain a major problem, particularly in cities.</p>	x	X				x
	The role of the car is changing	<p>There are evidences that show that the need for privately owned modes of transport is being replaced by a shared mobility culture where cars are seen as tools to be used on as-needed basis and no longer as property goods to be kept always available. Among younger people, car ownership is becoming increasingly less important and the number of millennials holding a driving license is notably dropping down. However, it is not clear whether, once the younger generations have become adults, the need for independent mobility will prevail over the environmental sensitivity and consumption styles typical of younger people, or whether new digital and artificial intelligence solutions will make less attractive or even unnecessary owned modes of transport.</p>			X			x
	Night trains make a comeback across Europe	<p>Night trains are on the rise again. 2021 marks the European Year of Rail and the resurrection of important new night train connections combined with fresh railway market entrants. In 2022, a new sleeper train will add to a network of planned routes that will link up cities across Europe, including Prague, Berlin and Amsterdam, Barcelona and Rome. A French start-up aims to run 'hotels on rails' from Paris to 12 cities across Europe, including Edinburgh, from 2024.</p>			X			x

Dimension	Trends and Signals	Description	P	E	S	T	L	E
Vehicles and systems	New mobility services are on the rise	Recent developments such as the Internet of Things (IoT), smart applications, along with emerging technologies, offer a whole range of new and innovative mobility solutions based on the sharing economy, to meet the fast-changing lifestyles of Europeans. Traditional players such as the automotive industry does no longer just produce cars, but also act as mobility providers, and the public transport companies overstep the boundaries of the 'traditional' public transport offer by becoming MaaS actors. New ownership models are seing the light, such as Vehicle on Demand (VoD), including car rental, car sharing and micro mobility services and Mobility on Demand (MoD), including demand-responsive transport, ride hailing and ride sharing .			x	X		
	Electrification, connection and automation are the priority for industry players	Industry players are accelerating the speed of automotive technology innovation as they develop new concepts of electric, connected, autonomous, and shared mobility. The industry has attracted more than \$400 billion in investments over the last decade—with about \$100 billion of that coming since the beginning of 2020. All this money targets companies and start-ups working on electrifying mobility, connecting vehicles, and autonomous driving technology. Such technology innovations will help reduce EV costs and make electric shared mobility a real alternative to owning a car. There are signs that electric and shared mobility need a harmonized urban regulation in order to provide the right incentive to the transition to electric mobility.				X	x	
	IoT and V2X play a crucial role in the transport system	Wireless communications will play a critical role in keeping the entire ecosystem of vehicles, infrastructure, and pedestrians in sync. Vehicles will increasingly observe what is happening around them, predict what is about to happen, communicate with each other, and take proactive safety measures to enhance road safety and reduce the number of accidents and pollution. IoT and V2X technologies permit the development of integrated transport systems, remote fleet management, autonomous driving, mobility-as-a-service (MaaS) solutions and many other smart (inter-)city solutions.			x	X		
	Airline companies become green concerned	For anyone who needs or wants to travel fast and far, flying is still the way to go. Google Flights announced it now includes estimated CO2 emissions in flight search results and on booking pages. In addition to sorting by price or duration, users can now sort by emission, and if trains are an option on their selected route, Google shows those as well.			X	x		

Dimension	Trends and Signals	Description	P	E	S	T	L	E
	Towards a ban of domestic flights where an alternative train route exists	In April 2021, French MPs have voted to suspend domestic airline flights on routes that can be travelled by direct train in less than two and a half hours, as part of a series of climate and environmental measures. France's new law will be watched closely by other countries. Austria's coalition conservative-green government introduced a €30 tax on airline tickets for flights of less than 217 miles (350km) last June and a ban on domestic flights that could be travelled in less than three hours by train.	X					x
	Towards autonomous train systems and Nnw generation of high-speed rail (Maglev and Hyperloop)	Companies like Nevomo in Poland and Zeleros in Spain are working towards drastically reduce travel times between major European cities at zero emissions by developing a hi-tech maglev rail system and a scalable Hyperloop system respectively.				X		
The city vision	Urban space is being reclaimed for pedestrian and other soft activities (not only transport)	Reclaiming urban public space, means reclaiming it in every sense, reclaiming the right to walk, to stroll, to loaf, to sit alone, to hang out with others, to wander, to get lost, to be visible, to be invisible, to use a toilet, to just be, in all those spaces, at all hours	X		x			X
	"Density" is reconsidered as a robust urban efficiency criterion/dogma	Compact cities are supposed to be more efficient and ensure better accessibility, but entail several drawbacks e.g. higher congestion levels, poor air quality in highly populated inner cities, stress	X	x	x			
	Citizen are increasingly involved in urban design, especially residential neighborhoods	Citizens are increasingly being engaged and invited to join in the processes of city planning, e.g. decisions on what improvements to spend money on (e.g. Helsinki) and re-design of residential streets (e.g. the Netherlands). The result can be a more sustainable and livable urban environment	X		x			
	Dystopian cityscapes and mobility concepts are used as the basis for urban planning	A rich, upper class lives in skyscrapers, using flying taxis (helicopters) for transport while workers live and work in terrible conditions on the ground. A two-class society is also be reflected in mobility patterns	X			X		
Social interaction	Widening inequality gap	Due to the pandemic local and global movements decreased leading towards a greater dispersion and segregation potentially widening the gap of inequality. The result of increasing inequality has been a rise in anger, nationalism, and drift away from the cooperative international framework. Segregation reduces empathy and will lead towards a stronger polarization of the society.			X			x
	Fear/Avoidance of crowded places	Right now an apparent immediate effect of the pandemics, but may be here to stay			X			

Dimension	Trends and Signals	Description	P	E	S	T	L	E
	Emerging awareness of the wide range of safety and security threats	As new transport modes and services will be interconnected, it will be important to consider how they can be safely integrated into the transport system, and vulnerable users can be protected.			X	x	X	
	Questioning the speed "mantra"	Moving from A to B entails other dimensions than time savings: people realise they can enjoy the trip <i>per se</i> (aesthetics, comfort) and that the best mobility choice is not only driven by individual time saved but by societal benefits		x	X			X

4 EXPLORATORY CONVERSATIONS AND MAIN OUTCOMES

As previously mentioned, the specific focus of REBALANCE on cultural and value-based determinants calls for a trend/signal identification process that goes beyond the scanning of “traditional” mobility focused sources. Accordingly, a series of exploratory conversations was staged with the involvement of thinkers and experts that can help delving into the deeper roots of mobility culture. The main purpose of these exploratory conversations was to validate and, most importantly, extend the scope and complement the trends and signals collected and classified in the initial horizon scanning step. In order to ensure good thematic coverage and consistency across conversations, each session followed an indicative script that was shared and agreed with the discussants beforehand. The indicative scripts are provided in [Annex 2](#).

The invited discussants contributed to the unveiling and characterizing of the philosophical and cultural backdrop against which mobility culture is shaped. These experts assisted REBALANCE to gain insight into possible future issues by digging into the current narrative associated to each topic and debating on whether there are any robust change factors that can help predict which direction or development will be favoured in the long term. Thus, REBALANCE aims to explore how our values, beliefs and aspirations will affect the development of each mobility topic or, conversely, how technological progress and expected developments will question our ingrained values and beliefs, and prompt cultural change.

The “Explorative conversations on the Mobility of the Future” were centred on five main themes, which are key in defining our future mobility:

1. Automated vehicles
2. Digitalisation
3. Towards greener transport choices
4. The future role of the car
5. Living, working and shopping patterns

4.1 Dialogue 1: Automated vehicles

Discussants: Ghadir Pourhashem (University of Žilina) and Cristina Pronello (Politecnico di Torino)

4.1.1 BACKGROUND

Automated vehicles (AV) are expected to release people from the technical constraint of driving and allow doing multiple tasks at the same time. Freedom and control are two major concepts that come into play when considering people’s reliance on automation. Passivity can easily be associated to a diminished experience of freedom or to loss of control. One of the most exploited arguments to overcome and compensate for this distrust is the alleged increase of road safety. The promised environmental benefits of driverless vehicles come often by the hand of shared mobility. This

innovative duo might become a successful symbiotic couple or, on the contrary, this partnership could hinder their diffusion.

Under the assumption that a cultural shift is needed before the massive adoption of AV, REBALANCE has identified, among others, a variety of ingrained cultural and value-driven attitudes that is likely to play a fundamental role in the future of AV, beyond their technological performance:

- Fear of innovation
- Fear of privacy breaches
- Fear of losing control
- Impoverishment of the human dimension of the travel experience
- Ethical issues

Many questions arise about whether and how to address these factors in order to impel people towards cultural shifts that would facilitate the uptake of AV. Some fear that forceful policies or nudges can initiate a slippery slope towards the dangers of an "ethical state".

The impact of vehicle automation on social inclusiveness remains uncertain. Further isolation and alienation cannot be ruled out. The paragon of the currently observed effects of Covid-19 on mobility choices might be valid once dictated whether they are transitory or permanent.

Regarding the technological aspect, the doubt appears when considering that most technologically innovative solutions for social and environmental sustainability are in fact mainly patching problems created by previous technological innovation. Until the identification of the outset of technological progress that intrinsically leads us to sustainability, current prevailing values (such as efficiency, speed, cost savings, technological progress "per se") perpetuate this headlong flight. The integration of technological progress will have to deal with two sets of goals, which are incompatible, or at least partly in contrast with one another:

- To increase speed and efficiency (cost, energy, time...)
- To increase comfort, safety and quality of life

The young generations are shifting priority values, but it is not clear yet how this translates into the adoption of technological innovation and, particularly in the case of AVs.

Beyond purely technological aspects, other factors could hinder the adoption of new technologies: Accidents and failures of self-driving vehicles, the fear of innovation, ethical issues.

4.1.2 MAIN OUTCOMES

Most relevant arguments that arose during the discussion include:

Technology

- Technologies are created for doing business and not for solving problems. AV or Electric vehicles are just an attempt by the automotive sector to stay alive.
- Scepticism to adopt new technologies because of lack of experience (or knowledge)

AV reliability

- Misconception and incoherence about the use of time in AV/public transport.
- Rejection to AV not related to fear of innovation but to the impossibility to reproduce human thinking and moral decisions. No confidence in the machine.
- AV in public transport is OK but in private transport is not OK (different perceptions)
- Socialisation (conviviality) thanks to AV goes with many question marks (gender, age gap)

Privacy and personal data

- Privacy issues with personal data and sharing technologies.
- No data publicly available for innovations and research.

Governance

- Confidence of the public in policy-makers.
- Presentation to the public of possible options (data, conclusions...)
- Targeted nudges.

Aspirational values

- The most important trip one person does associated to emotion/pleasure. Pleasure of driving, preference for driving oneself.
- Improvement of quality of life versus optimisation and misperceived opinions as facts.
- Fear of loss of control.
- Fear to change habits.
- Social inclusion will not come by sharing.

4.2 Dialogue 2: Digitalisation

Discussants: Benjamin Docquir (Osborne Clarke) and Xavier Tackoen (Espaces-Mobilités)

4.2.1 BACKGROUND

Mobility services, whether for passengers or goods, are increasingly relying on ICT-based solutions, which are supposed to increase economic efficiency, safety, and the environmental performance of the transport system. This clear and unchallenged perspective does not take into account obstacles and undesired implications such as a loss of privacy, a decrease in social interaction opportunities or widening inequalities that leave some people behind.

Pursuing the digital and green transition, the so-called “twin transition”, has now become a widespread policy mantra. In the transport sector, there are obvious synergies between the digital and the green dimensions, but there are also potential challenges in combining the two. Therefore, there is the need to identify and negotiate eventual tradeoffs.

When it comes to leveraging individual and collective motivations to promote sustainable mobility, two approaches can be followed: one is to build upon the efficiency of digital solutions and the other is to lean on environmental concerns and awareness.

Smart working, on-line shopping and other “e-life” solutions enabled by digitalization are often promoted as directly instrumental and beneficial to sustainability, including increased safety and higher economic efficiency. Some argue that this is a delusion as undesired consequences arise, for instance:

- Does the ease of use brought in by digital services generate a rebound effect and boost “non-essential” mobility?
- Just-in-time practices optimize the use of space (with economic benefits for the industry) but increase the number of trips and of v.km
- More generally, does the digitalization of transport and new delivery patterns inevitably lead to a reduction of pax.km but an increase in ton.km?
- Is there such a thing as “good vs bad efficiency”?

Covid-19 has significantly changed mobility patterns, for both goods (on-line shopping) and passengers (smart working). These were enabled by digitalization, but there is no certainty whether these changes will be sustained when pandemics is under control. People have developed a fear of crowded spaces, although they not seem prepared to give up the social benefits of physical mobility. Anyhow, we could be heading towards an overall less convivial life.

Privacy concerns arise from the obligation to share personal data to be able to use or benefit from digital mobility services. People might seem more afraid of “Big Brother”

than they actually are, given the global spread of social networks. The battle between efficiency and privacy is not decided.

Digital-enabled solutions such as MAAS and Transport-on-Demand services are designed to better meet individual needs, but this objective could be hindered by the digital divide that will either leave some groups behind (vulnerable people, elderly, technology-unsavvy...) or rather, by make it easier and cheaper to move around, therefore favouring inclusivity. Gaps could appear between "physical" public (planners, decision-makers) and "virtual" private (service providers) approaches. Another relevant issue is access to digital mobility services being constrained by the quasi-monopolistic position of a small number of providers (e.g. GAFA).

4.2.2 MAIN OUTCOMES

Most relevant arguments that arose during the discussion include:

Technology

- Trust as a key for adopting new technologies.
- Digitalisation as a mean and sustainability as a goal, but not reflected in reality.
- Covid-19 helped realise that technology is an enabler.

Privacy and personal data

- Personal data will be shared if asked in a smart way, but there will also be more use awareness.
- Data needed by operators and planners (public interest).
- Not much confidence in the mobility app.

Efficiency

- Cycling embraced because of efficiency (and socialisation) and not environment conscience
- Speed is fun, not efficiency
- Redefine efficiency from economic to welfare of society

Governance

- Transparency by the decision-makers
- Regulation comes too early (kills innovation) or too late (monsters surge)

Society

- Change behaviours with education, training (raising awareness), digitalisation comes last
- Individual freedom articulates many behaviours, choices
- People at the centre but digital gap will not disappear

- Inclusion before digitalisation and not because of it
- Gatekeepers, nudging not sufficient
- Group needs and diversity needs
- Local benefits overshadowed by global externalities (cyclists make more long distance travels)

Aspirational values

- Understanding the stakes/awareness
- Diversity of options (e.g. opt-in & opt-out)
- Usable time
- "I want to master my mobility"
- From JIT to as fast as possible (and from companies to consumers)

4.3 Dialogue 3: Towards greener transport choices

Discussants: Andreu Ulied (Ersilia Foundation) and Robert Braun (Institute for Advanced Studies-IHS)

4.3.1 BACKGROUND

In Europe, signs towards greener transport choices are emerging. Industry is making cleaner vehicles increasingly available and performant (electromobility, cleaner fuels) and government plays an important role through standards, taxation, phasing out, but also, at the local level, through the redesign of urban, greener spaces and infrastructure. The question to be answered is whether these moves are in fact primarily pushed forward by a changing societal attitude towards environment protection and the pursuance of a healthier life. If not, it should be measured how effective would be a green mobility transition without a major shift in the attitude of citizens and mobility users.

Grassroots initiatives, like "Fridays for Future", are playing an important role in raising environmental and health concerns, which in turn could foster modal shifts. To which extent people are really driven by knowledge and evidence on the social and environmental benefits of green choices, or is it rather the urge to fulfil social norms that drives them is something that will be revealed in the near future. Moreover, the success of such initiatives might also contribute to underline intergenerational differences in awareness and motivation.

Paradigm changes are very slow. However, if we manage to imagine a new mobility culture based on structural changes, we should ask ourselves whether demand-side policies today in place - such as access regulations, infrastructure charging, standards - will be no longer necessary.

The shift towards "active travel" is a major component of the green transition. Active travel is usually defined as travel that requires physical activity (walking, cycling etc.),

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generating social benefits in both environmental and health terms. REBALANCE aims to comprehend the depth of the changes in values and attitudes that are required to enact a visible move to active travel. On the other hand, travel choices can be influenced by the extent to which the traveler is allowed to be “the actor”, making all decisions (direction, speed, stops, changes of plan etc.). In that case, private cars are the ones that allow maximum “agency” and control. The final element of the active scene is the advent of micromobility, which can be a substitute for private, or – more worryingly – also a substitute for physically active modes, or even cover a new transitional zone between both modes.

Gender issues are also addressed to understand if gender is a meaningful variable in the transition to greener mobility. If so, does this have to do with gender-specific value differences?

A contemporary debate cannot omit the influence of Covid-19 on mobility and the plausibility that it yields structural behavioural changes, a “new normal” where substantial modal shifts become permanent. A case is thrown on the table: the role of air travel after Covid-19:

- Rising awareness of its ecological footprint vs. revitalisation of leisure travel
- Business travels vs Zoom meetings
- Ban of domestic flights where an alternative train route exists
- Night trains back in fashion?

4.3.2 MAIN OUTCOMES

Most relevant arguments that arose during the discussion include:

Technology

- Remote technologies have an impact on socialisation, creativity and new projects
- We are not in control when entangled with different technologies

Active travel

- Inequalities and (how they relate to) active travel
- Active mobility is great for upper middle class men, but not so much for the majority. It also brings a lot of externalities
- Walking for socialisation

Mobility systems

- Industry push towards allegedly sustainable modes that are nothing new
- Transition to electricity is being forced by coercion, not by awareness
- Mobility systems have an immense resilience and capability of incorporating critique

- Short-haul and city aerial mobility will become a major problem

Governance

- Regime change is necessary to change the 'details' (environment, mobility...). New regime less based on command-control and more based on collaboration-moral economy.
- Top-down is the enemy (totalitarian paradigm)
- Transition organised with the people (from legal norms to social norms)

Society

- Paradigm change is extremely slow
- Inequalities hidden by the environmental imaginary (new technologies do not solve all problems and create new ones)
- Clean, circular, sustainable suburbs where people are disconnected and live alone
- There is no culture-nature divide. Reconceptualise the world around us
- Covid-19: New normal will be very similar to old normal

Gender

- Women as indicator of transport service quality
- Transport and public spaces should be evaluated through women's involvement and the services provided

Aspirational values

- Value choices are more important than technology when changing mobility modes
- Environmental consciousness vs imaginary

4.4 Dialogue 4: The future role of the car

Discussants: Jens Schade (Technische Universitaet Dresden-TUD) and Stefan Gössling (Lund University)

4.4.1 BACKGROUND

Private car use is recognized as having significant negative impacts on environment, health, and safety. It generates congestion, consumes significant urban space and affects quality of life in general. Access regulation, initiatives to foster active mobility and micromobility, and to make public transport more attractive address some of these concerns. But private car ownership and use is deeply ingrained in our culture, and car sales keep growing. REBALANCE explores the congruity of a perspective consisting in a radical shift away from cars and the "key values" that should be promoted in order to achieve it.

Driving a car is perceived as an expression of freedom: the driver is “in control”, can decide where, when, at what speed, and with what itinerary to move around. Although, this is sometimes a delusion, when suffering frustrating congestion, time losses to find parking spots, impotence in avoiding accidents provoked by others, along with high economic costs. “Agency” is arguably a fundamental determinant of mobility choices. Nevertheless, it is worth researching how more and better evidence of real costs and benefits, both individual and collective, could help deconstructing the current paradigm, and convincing people that their real need is to move, not to drive.

It is often stated that the main reason behind the prevalence of private car use is the “status symbol” notion attached to the car, and the subsequent reticence to give up ownership. The emergence of shared vehicles and shared rides schemes can be optimistically interpreted as a promising signal in this regard. In order to become prevalent, “soft spots” in people’s values and perception must be addressed for this to happen, also considering the “generation gap” and differentiated perspectives across age groups. On the other hand, if it is sustained, the generalized acceptance of shared schemes could lead car use to become an integral part of more sustainable, multimodal and seamless mobility patterns. This would then further rule out any perspective of phasing out cars as such! Ultimately, a radical shift to shared schemes could not be enough to curb the dramatic impacts of automobility.

Technological innovation is mostly presented as a promising pathway towards sustainability: cleaner propulsion, vehicle automation, “smart”, ICT-based mobility can undoubtedly bring - if only incremental - improvements in environmental and safety-related performances of transport systems and services. This could simply mean a further step towards the consolidation of the car-based mobility culture, one that in the end definitively precludes a radical shift away from automobility. And even worse, technological progress could generate perverse rebound effects which would ultimately mainly serve the interests of the automotive industry rather than those of society.

The urge to avoid crowded transport solutions due to Covid-19, has at least partially overshadowed what was observed, only a few years ago, as a progressive disenchantment with car ownership and use, especially among the young. To minimize contact with others, many people are choosing to travel in their own vehicles. Since the outbreak of Covid-19 the use of public transportation and carpools has declined significantly worldwide. Whether Covid-related concerns are an alibi to sticking to private car use, where all collective modes, but also shared cars, are perceived as a health risk or – especially among the younger generations – is the fallback on private car mobility only a “minor evil”, to get rid of as swiftly as possible has yet to be seen.

4.4.2 MAIN OUTCOMES

Most relevant arguments that arose during the discussion include:

Urban space

- Every bicycle creates space
- Progressive city dwellers
- Concentrate on the progressive part of big cities to support change

- Politicians (and the electoral agenda) are one of the main barriers for car-free cities. Big cities are more into it
- Cities are the place to start implementing alternatives
- Cycling must be improved
- Safe spaces are needed to allow people (who are willing) to switch from cars to bicycles

Sharing

- Car sharing AV could increase traffic and create additional problems
- The future of sharing will depend on convenience (and availability)

Car industry

- Powerful automotive industries in some countries (Germany, Italy) convey a message of car dependency, much more than real necessity
- Changes are easier in countries without a car industry (The Netherlands, Denmark)

Society

- Change will not be fast, but resistance can grow quickly
- Awareness of wrong policy direction
- Western societies do not accept restrictions well. Indirect measures (price, parking...) could work but will not lead to structural changes
- Vast majority of the population accepted Covid restrictions, why not in other cases?
- Need to be open to address taboos like speed limits, driving licences renewal of elder people
- Education to give information and awareness
- Subsidies and internalisation (of external costs and benefits)

Aspirational values

- Europeans are free but many feel oppressed, why?
- Freedom is just economic freedom
- Give immediate feedback on your behaviour does have an effect. Costs do not steer behaviour because they are indirect and invisible
- The car is part of one's personality, showing the real economic cost and impact will not change anything
- Possession has its own value
- Ownership will be more determinant than electric or autonomous
- Safety and self-protection discourses, cars fit in

- People make rational choices and change behaviours when given enough information
- Sustainable trends from Covid? Young people are becoming more conservative, could become more attached to cars and car ownership

4.5 Dialogue 5: Living, working and shopping patterns

Disussants: Alain L’Hostis (Université Gustave Eiffel) and Cristina Marolda (Independent expert, former EC Officer in charge of Research and Innovative Transport Systems)

4.5.1 BACKGROUND

Living, working and shopping patterns are changing in Europe and transforming our urban context. As ICT-based technology permeates our life, the so-called “smart” solutions become the default option for many people, supposedly bringing time savings and overall efficiency gains. Pandemics has certainly accelerated this change, but a more structural trend was visible even before, which technological innovation alone cannot explain. The implications are far-reaching, they affect urban form, infrastructure requirements, and most importantly basic values such as equality of opportunities

REBALANCE want to know to which of the following four “models” are the aspirations of the majority of citizens – and specifically of young generations - aligned with:

- Suburban dwelling, quiet, more indoor and outdoor space
- Inner city dwelling, “where the action is”
- Rural escape, return to nature
- 15-minute city, multi-nodal city

One way to predict which of these will be favoured in the long term is to identify robust change factors that support them.

Regarding the debate “comfort vs convenience”, efficiency, in the guise of “individual convenience”, appears to be the main driver of changing patterns. The level of extent to which efficiency is pursued at the expense of other fundamental values and aspirations, both at the individual level (comfort) and more importantly at the overall community level (equity, conviviality) needs to be explored.

The concept of “value of time” is gaining ground. Awareness of mobility injustice is spreading. Long commuting times, in particular, reflect differently on different-economic groups, and attention is growing on “kinetic elites” and other inequality risks. Urban density has been systematically equated with efficiency -quicker accessibility-, which leads to a disregard towards urban sprawl. The revision of this dogma could put polycentric cities on the spotlight in the matter of reducing mobility injustice.

The massive shift towards remote activities (work, learn, shop etc.) entails that the availability of individual space becomes a prominent concern. The following two extreme alternatives fight to prevail:

1. Alternative 1: the shift towards remote, virtual life is here to stay. It is therefore necessary to redesign our space and the logistics available in order to ensure comfort and efficiency in the medium/long-term. The real estate market undergoes a major structural change, with residential space in higher demand while office space loses value.
2. Alternative 2: confinements and lockdowns have shown that the social/convivial dimensions of most of our activities are essential to ensure an acceptable quality of life. Remote work and education are limited to the essential and a majority of people/families are content with marginal readjusting of their available space

Will urban expansion drive the evolution of transport infrastructure and mobility services, or the other way around?

4.5.2 MAIN OUTCOMES

Most relevant arguments that arose during the discussion include:

Urban paradigm

- Rural escape from the city centre
- 15 min city (multinodal, multicenter)
- 4 dwelling models
- State market has grown exponentially
- Cities should be balanced between density and green spaces
- Dutch model: small cities connected. It should be explored
- Polycentric cities reduce transport injustice or just increase efficiency? Services must be guaranteed for the majority and not just for the elite
- Millennials wanted to settle in the inner city but couldn't afford it
- Digitalisation and gentrification define the city models or the other way around?
- Denser cities because the human population continues to grow

Technology

- Smart does not equal digital
- The need to be aware of technology, ingrained in society
- Things are changing, also the assumptions. Technology must be steered because it is not fair per se
- Digitalisation in the sense of remote behaviour

Efficiency

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- Optimisation of mobility in the case of freedom of choice or not the case?
- Optimisation is not an individual choice
- Value of travel time will mean less commuting time? (VTT reduces when using ICT). But value of time is rooted in efficiency
- People will travel more when commuting

Society

- 3 young generations. Millennials adapt and enjoy space
- Possible divide in society between commuters and non-commuters. Also possible a combination of both, with occasional commuting (with longer travel times)
- Differences of needs and wishes between generations
- z-gen digital natives can live everywhere, isolated with internet
- Social networks, meeting people is a driver?
- Teens in France reduced their mobility for leisure (even before Covid)
- Differences between manual and intellectual work. Do not fall into bourgeois perspectives
- Environmental consciousness and sustainability, specially by the young
- The need to be aware of the common good, not as a synonym of reduction of freedom

Aspirational values

- Millennials do not put effort into owning the car
- Convenience (efficiency instead of comfort) affects other values?
- Social sustainability, economic sustainability and environment sustainability (top-down, awareness campaigns, nuances)
- Inequalities: awareness of transport injustice related to density vs sprawl
- Long impact of Covid: we revaluated the value of personal time, we slowed down. We have rethought our priorities

4.6 Trends and signals from explorative conversations

Based on the outcomes of the exploratory conversations, a further set of trends and signals were ultimately identified, that complement those emerging from the initial horizon scanning.

Table 2 below presents this additional set of trends and signals and – for the sake of consistency – shows them in the same format than those in Table 1. On the other hand, the purpose of the exploratory conversations was to tackle issues that are at the outset illustrating possible changes in values, beliefs and attitudes, which reflects on the nature of these additional trends/signals, closer to the ultimate core discussion on mobility culture and the underlying values

TABLE2: Trends and Signals from the explorative conversations

Dimension	Trends and Signals	Description	P	E	S	T	L	E
Lifestyles	Scepticism towards new technologies by the elder or the poorer	Scepticism to adopt new technologies because of lack of experience, knowledge or purchasing power. Even if people are at the centre of new technological advances, the digital gap will not disappear.		x	x	X		
	As fast as possible	Companies abandon JIT to deliver as fast as possible. The focus is shifted from other companies to consumers.		X				
	Raising awareness of the sharing of personal data	Privacy issues with personal data and sharing technologies are on the rise. People tend to show little confidence in mobility apps. This could lead to having no data publicly available for innovation and research. Data are needed by operators and planners, which become in turn a matter of public interest. Personal data will be shared if asked in a smart way, but there will also be more use awareness.			X		x	
	Long impact of Covid-19 on the value of personal time	We reevaluated the value of personal time, we slowed down. We have rethought our priorities. Covid-19 helped realise that technology is an enabler			X			
	Digitalisation as a mean and sustainability as a goal	It is not yet reflected in reality. Change behaviours with education, training (raising awareness), then digitalisation comes last. Understanding the stakes/awareness.			x	X		
Travel habits	Change on the value of travel time	New perceptions on the value of travel time could mean less commuting time but it also reduces when using ICT. However, value of time is rooted in efficiency. People will travel more when commuting. Concept of usable time			X			

Dimension	Trends and Signals	Description	P	E	S	T	L	E
Modal choices	Cycling embracement	Cycling is embraced because of efficiency (and socialisation) and not environment conscience. However, local benefits are overshadowed by global externalities (cyclists make more long distance travels). Safe spaces are needed to allow people (who are willing) to switch from cars to bicycles. Every bicycle creates space.			X			x
	Women as indicator of transport service quality	Transport and public spaces should be evaluated through women's involvement and the services provided			X			
	Active mobility for the privileged	Active mobility consolidates among upper middle class men, but not so much within the majority. It also brings lots of externalities. Walking for socialisation is only possible in safe environments			X			
Vehicles and systems	Industry push towards electric vehicles	Industrial giants push towards allegedly sustainable modes that are not so new. Transition to electricity is being forced by coercion, not by awareness. Mobility systems have an immense resilience and capability of incorporating critique.		X		x		
	The European automotive industry conveys a message of car dependency for economic and safety reasons	Powerful automotive industries in some countries (Germany, Italy) convey a message of car dependency, much more than real necessity. Changes are easier in countries without a car industry (The Netherlands, Denmark) where national pride is not an element of the equation. Safety and self-protection discourses, cars fit in. Subsidies and internalisation (of external costs and benefits)	x	X				

Dimension	Trends and Signals	Description	P	E	S	T	L	E
	Car ownership on the rise	Car ownership has been legitimated by Covid-19 in the sense of self-protection. World sales have increased. The car is part of one's personality, showing the real economic cost and impact will not change anything. Give immediate feedback on your behaviour does have an effect. Costs do not steer behaviour because they are indirect and invisible. Possession has its own value. Ownership will be more determinant than electric or autonomous. Young people are becoming more conservative, could become more attached to cars and car ownership		x	X			x
	Rejection of AV	Rejection to AV not related to fear of innovation but to the impossibility to reproduce human thinking and moral decisions that leads to not having confidence in the machine. AV in public transport is OK but in private transport is not OK because of different perceptions. The most important trip one person does is associated to emotion/pleasure. Trust is key for adopting new technologies.			X	x		
The city vision	15-minute city projects	More and more European cities are debating new multimodal, multicentre approaches. The Dutch model with small cities connected is being explored. Polycentric cities as a way to reduce transport injustice (and increase efficiency?)	X		x			
	Car-free cities	Cities are the place to start implementing alternatives to classical transport and mobility. Big cities are more into it. Politicians (and the electoral agenda) are one of the main barriers for car-free cities. Concentrate on the progressive part of big cities to support change.	X		x			x

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Dimension	Trends and Signals	Description	P	E	S	T	L	E
Social interaction	Free but oppressed	Europeans are essentially free but many feel oppressed. Western societies do not accept restrictions well. The vast majority of the population accepted Covid-19 restrictions, but not in other cases. Need to be open to address taboos like speed limits, driving licences renewal of elder people. Indirect measures to reduce traffic or pollution (price, parking...) could work but will not lead to structural changes. Freedom is just economic freedom	x		X			
	Remote technologies impact on socialisation, creativity and new projects	We are not in control when entangled with different technologies. Diversity of options (e.g. opt-in & opt-out). Social inclusion will not come by sharing. Socialisation (conviviality) thanks to AV goes with many question marks (gender, age gap).				X		
	Citizens demand transparency and active roles in the decision-making process	Regime change is necessary to change the 'details' (environment, mobility...). New regime less based on command-control and more based on collaboration-moral economy. Transition organised with the people (from legal norms to social norms). Paradigm change is extremely slow. Top-down is the enemy (totalitarian paradigm). People make rational choices and change behaviours when given enough information. Presentation to the public of possible options (data, conclusions...). Change will not be fast, but resistance can grow quickly. Regulation comes too early (kills innovation) or too late (monsters surge).	X		x		x	

Dimension	Trends and Signals	Description	P	E	S	T	L	E
	Generation gap of needs and wishes	Differences of needs and wishes between generations. Differences between manual and intellectual work. The risk of taking bourgeois perspectives when addressing social problems. Possible divide in society between commuters and non-commuters.			X			
	Social demands for services for all	Services must be guaranteed for the majority and not just for the elite. Group needs and diversity needs. Redefine efficiency from economic to welfare of society. Inequalities: awareness of transport injustice related to density vs sprawl. Education to give information and awareness. Inclusion comes before digitalisation and not because of it.	X					
	Environmental consciousness vs imaginary	Inequalities hidden by the environmental imaginary (new technologies do not solve all problems and create new ones). Inequalities and (how they relate to) active travel. Environmental consciousness and sustainability, especially by the young. The need to be aware of technology, ingrained in society. The need to be aware of the common good, not as a synonym of reduction of freedom. Social sustainability, economic sustainability and environment sustainability (top-down, awareness campaigns, nuances)			x			X

5 FROM TRANSPORT AND MOBILITY TRENDS TO CULTURAL AND VALUE DRIVERS

As previously noted, trends and signals identified through the horizon scanning - and complemented with the insights gathered in the exploratory conversations – can vary in terms of:

- The scale and scope of the phenomenon they describe
- The extent to which they explicitly point at (possible) changes in value and cultural tenets

In order to effectively pave the way towards the identification of a usable set of drivers, Table 3 below presents a consolidated list of trends/signals where each of them is further characterised in terms of its meaningfulness for - and relevance to - cultural tenets and underlying values.

TABLE3: Consolidated list of trends/signals characterised in terms of meaningfulness for/relevance to cultural tenets and underlying values.

	Trends and Signals	Relevance to culture and values
Lifestyles	Urban exodus, younger generations get away from cities	Fleeing from unsustainable urban life/pace Back to nature Quality of life more important than efficiency
	Polytopic living is accelerating	Changing definition of comfort and convenience
	Flexible remote work is on the rise	Flexibility/adaptability as a positive value
	Business and lack of leisure time become a status symbol	Appearance prevails
	Consumption and shopping patterns are in continuous evolution	Changing definition of comfort and convenience
	Increasing awareness of the environmental impact of transport influences decisions of customers to buy locally	Priority to sustainability (awareness)
	Scepticism towards new technologies by the elder or the poorer	Increasing inequalities Widening Digital gap
	As fast as possible	Changing perception of the value of (individual) time
	Raising awareness of the sharing of personal data	Increased concerns about personal privacy and security Individual contribution to common interests
	Long impact of Covid on the value of personal time	Changing perception of the value of (individual) time
Travel habits	Digitalisation as a mean and sustainability as a goal	Increased reliance on virtual solutions Education as a tool for cultural change
	Reductions in daily mobility and long-distance domestic travel are observed among the young	Increased reliance on virtual solutions
	Leisure travel remains high-carbon	Price and time habits
	Leisure travel is booming after the pandemic	Mobility as a privilege
	Business travel is in structural decline	Flexibility/adaptability as a positive value
Modal choices	Change on the value of travel time	Changing perception of the value of (individual) time
	Usage of bikes as means of transport is growing significantly due to the pandemic	Changing definition of comfort and convenience Sustainable and healthier urban life
	People is expected to use (e)scooters more frequently	Changing definition of comfort and convenience Sustainable and healthier urban life
	The use of public transportation is declining due to the pandemic	Safety at the top Emergence of the notion of "useful mobility"
	The role of the car is changing	Less attention to status symbols, priority to sustainability (awareness)

		Substance (functionality, sustainability) prevails over appearance
	Night trains make a comeback across Europe	Quality of life more important than efficiency Changing definition of comfort and convenience
	Cycling embracement	Less attention to status symbols, priority to sustainability (awareness) Substance (functionality, sustainability) prevails over appearance Sustainable and healthier urban life
	Women as indicator of transport service quality	Feminist and gender approaches Mobility injustice
	Active mobility for the privileged	Mobility injustice Sustainable and healthier urban life Increased value attached to comfort, sustainability, health as opposed to efficiency
Vehicles and systems	New mobility services are on the rise	Love of car and perception of freedom and privacy associated to the car-centred culture prevail, even when not privately owned
	Electrification, connection and automation are the priority for industry players	Efficiency and technology at the top
	IoT and V2X play a crucial role in the transport system	Safety at the top
	Airline companies become green concerned	Priority to sustainability (awareness) Functionality prevails over appearance
	Towards a ban of domestic flights where an alternative train route exists	Sustainable and healthier life
	Towards autonomous train systems and new generation of high-speed rail (Maglev and Hyperloop)	Efficiency and technology at the top
Vehicles and systems	Industry push towards electric vehicles	Love of car and perception of freedom Status symbol
	The European automotive industry conveys a message of car dependency for economic and safety reasons	Love of car and perception of freedom Status symbol Increased concerns about personal health and security
	Car ownership on the rise	Love of car and perception of freedom Status symbol Increased concerns about personal health and security Direct information and feedback on economic costs, impacts and externalities

	Rejection to AV	Distrust in AI Fear of loss of control Pleasure of driving
The city vision	Urban space is being reclaimed for pedestrian and other soft activities (not only transport)	Quality of life Changing the common vision of the city
	"Density" is reconsidered as a robust urban efficiency criterion/dogma	Low rise urban landscapes valued for better aesthetics, access to natural light
	Citizen are increasingly involved in urban design, especially residential neighborhoods	Increasing citizens' aspiration to play an active role
	Dystopian cityscapes and mobility concepts are used as the basis for urban planning	Changing the common vision of the city Sustainable and healthier urban life
	15-minute city projects	Quality of life Conviviality and social life Changing the common vision of the city Changing definition of comfort and convenience
Car-free cities	Sustainable and healthier urban life Changing the common vision of the city Changing definition of comfort and convenience	
Social interaction	Widening inequality gap	Increasing inequalities and mobility injustice
	Fear/Avoidance of crowded places	Increased concerns about health safety
	Emerging awareness of the wide range of safety and security threats	Increased concerns about personal privacy and security
	Questioning the speed "mantra"	Increased value attached to comfort, sustainability, as opposed to efficiency Changing perception of the value of (individual) time
	Free but oppressed	Individualism Rights are taken for granted, obligations are despised Increased concerns about personal privacy and security Direct information and feedback on economic costs, impacts and externalities
	Remote technologies impact on socialisation, creativity and new projects	Increased reliance on virtual solutions Virtual substitution of reality
Citizens demand transparency and active roles in the decision-making process	Increasing citizens' aspiration to play an active role Cherished democracy	

	Generation gap of needs and wishes	Mobility injustice Increasing inequality
	Social demands for services for all	Mobility injustice Education as a tool for cultural change Collective protection of the common good
	Environmental consciousness vs imaginary	Environmental awareness Wider concept of sustainability Protection of the common good

The ultimate goal of the extended horizon scanning described above was to devise a list of drivers from which to further select a shorter list of critical uncertainties that can be used to define the REBALANCE scenario space.

In line with the specific ambition of the project, and as opposed to what can be found in previous transport foresight exercises, the REBALANCE drivers must be explicitly related to culture and value changes.

Accordingly, the long list of drivers presented in Table 3 above was further elaborated. Trends and signals were thus clustered around a shorter list of individual and collective aspirations, reflecting alternative philosophical views, ethical priorities and diverse cultural inheritance.

Table 4 below presents the outcome of this further elaboration

Table 4: Clustering of trends and signals

Values and beliefs reflected in trends and signals	Attitude towards...	Range of variation
Fleeing from unsustainable urban life/pace	Living environment	Back to nature Vs Urban action
Back to nature		
Virtual substitution of reality		
Quality of life more important than efficiency	Life's steering principle	Quality of life, comfort, conviviality Vs Efficiency
Changing definition of comfort and convenience		
Increased acceptance of limiting conviviality opportunities		
Increased value attached to comfort, sustainability, as opposed to efficiency		
Increasing citizens' aspiration to play an active role	Empowerment	Individual and collective empowerment Vs "Go with the flow"
Shifting the focus from the preciousness and scarcity of goods to the preciousness and scarcity of individuals.		
Increased reliance on virtual solutions	Technoscientific society	Trust in technology Vs Fear of innovation
Distrust in AI		
Emergence of the notion of "useful mobility"	Useful mobility	Moving only when necessary Vs Moving as much as possible
Flexibility/adaptability as a positive value		
Changing perception of the value of (individual) time		
Mobility injustice	Equity	Reducing inequalities as a priority goal Vs Mobility as a privilege
Increasing inequalities and mobility injustice		
Feminist and gender approaches		
Widening Digital gap		

Values and beliefs reflected in trends and signals	Attitude towards...	Range of variation
Low rise urban landscapes valued for better aesthetics, access to natural light	Urban liveability	Environmental sustainability as the priority Vs Dense and efficient urban fabric
Changing the common vision of the city		
Less attention to status symbols, priority to sustainability (awareness); functionality prevails over appearance		
Safety at the top	Safety perspective	Safety as a collective, societal priority Vs Safety as a marginal concern
Increased concerns about health safety		
Increased concerns about personal privacy and security	Privacy concerns	Privacy protection as a priority Vs Acceptance of privacy limitations
Individual contribution to common interests		
Love of car and perception of freedom and privacy associated to the car-centred culture prevail, even when not privately owned	Car-based culture	Unsustainability of car-based culture vs Individual car as the superior option to ensure freedom
Pleasure of driving		
Status symbol		
Citizens' democratic and participatory aspirations	Participation	Participatory governance Vs Radical individualism
Collective protection of the common good		
Radical individualism, repudiation of norms and obligations		
Education as a tool for cultural change	Sustainability transition	Cultural change Vs Market-driven actions
Direct information and feedback on economic costs, impacts and externalities		

6 WAY FORWARD: ANTICIPATING THE SCENARIO FRAMEWORK

The next step of the scenario building process is the identification of the critical uncertainties that should be used to define the scenario space. Critical uncertainties (CU) will be selected among the drivers identified above and summarised below:

TABLE 5: REBALANCE Drivers

Drivers
Living environment
Life's steering principle
Empowerment
Technoscientific society
Useful mobility
Equity
Urban liveability
Safety perspective
Privacy concerns
Car-based culture
Participation
Sustainability transition

The CU selection will be carried out through a review process internal to the project consortium, which will serve the dual purpose of:

- a. Validating, and possibly refining (sharpness, wording) the above list
- b. Ranking

To ensure that the scenarios illustrate real, contrasted alternatives, a simple survey will be carried out where respondents will be asked to rank each of the drivers according to two main criteria:

- Importance/relevance: to what extent the positioning of the driver between its two extremes is likely to affect the shaping of future mobility (high vs low impact)
- Uncertainty: to what extent is the future dynamics of the driver predictable (high predictability would result in a scenario invariant, while high uncertainty

allows to devise sufficiently contrasted visions of the future, thereby opening the door to more decisive policy interventions)

The drivers that are ranked higher based on the combination of the two scores will be considered for the definition of the scenario space.

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ANNEX 1 - REFERENCES

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	Polytopic living is accelerating	Kaufmann, V. 2016. From weak signals to mobility scenarios
	Flexible remote work is on the rise	https://www.economicsobservatory.com/what-is-the-future-of-working-from-home https://home.kpmg/xx/en/home/insights/2021/08/kpmg-2021-ceo-outlook.html
	Business and lack of leisure time become a status symbol	https://www.hbs.edu/faculty/Pages/item.aspx?num=51948
	Consumption and shopping patterns are in continuous evolution	Monitor Deloitte, 2020
	Increasing awareness of the environmental impact of transport influences decisions of customers to buy locally	https://www.warc.com/newsandopinion/news/localism-is-forecast-to-be-a-major-post-pandemic-trend/43612 https://www.logobrand.com/why-is-it-important-for-brands-and-retailers-to-respond-to-localism-availability-and-consciously-sourcing-have-a-direct-correlation-to-localism-availability-across-local-stores-is-there/

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	People is expected to use (e)scooters more frequently	https://www.ft.com/content/49d05f0f-5391-4608-8cd3-08fb6ce4f2fe https://www.ft.com/content/5559f016-1f9f-4fab-9020-71e69c6debc3
	The use of public transportation is declining due to the pandemic	https://www.automotiveworld.com/news-releases/continental-mobility-study-2020-increasing-importance-of-private-transportation-during-the-pandemic/ https://www.itsinternational.com/its17/news/private-cars-may-be-more-popular-post-covid-experts-warn

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	Night trains make a comeback across Europe	https://www.dw.com/en/night-trains-make-a-comeback-across-europe/a-57878517 https://www.theguardian.com/travel/2021/jun/22/new-network-of-european-sleeper-overnight-trains-planned https://www.timeout.com/news/europe-is-getting-a-ton-of-cool-new-sleeper-trains-120820 https://www.lonelyplanet.com/articles/night-train-network-europe-expansion
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	Electrification, connection and automation are the priority for industry players	https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/automotive-and-assembly/our-insights/why-the-automotive-future-is-electric

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	IoT and V2X play a crucial role in the transport system	https://www.keysight.com/es/en/assets/7018-06580/white-papers/5992-3857.pdf https://www.einfochips.com/blog/faqs-on-automotive-iot/
	Airline companies become green concerned	http://info.trendwatching.com/innovation-of-the-day/lite-flights-lowest-co2-emissions https://www.airlinetrends.com/
	Towards a ban of domestic flights where an alternative train route exists	https://www.euractiv.com/section/aviation/news/france-to-ban-some-domestic-flights-where-train-available/ https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-56716708
	Towards autonomous train systems	https://www.startus-insights.com/innovators-guide/top-10-rail-industry-trends-innovations-2021-beyond/ https://interestingengineering.com/life-in-2050-a-glimpse-at-transportation-in-the-future
	New generation of high-speed rail (Maglev and Hyperloop) are seeing the light	https://www.economist.com/europe/2021/11/13/how-trains-could-replace-planes-in-europe https://www.euronews.com/next/2021/09/14/paris-to-berlin-in-an-hour-welcome-to-the-future-of-rail-travel-in-europe
The city vision	Urban space is being reclaimed for pedestrian and other soft activities (not only transport)	https://medium.com/@irasanyal/activating-and-reclaiming-public-spaces-efaceffa1279#:~:text=Reclaiming%20urban%20public%20space%2C%20means,those%20spaces%2C%20at%20all%20hours
	“Density” is reconsidered as a robust urban efficiency criterion/dogma	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/294090560_Sustainable_Living_and_Urban_Density_The_Choices_are_Wide_Open

	Trends and Signals	References
	Dystopian cityscapes and mobility concepts are used as the basis for urban planning	https://newatlas.com/science-fiction-cities-future-urban-visions-architecture/55569/ https://www.inverse.com/article/18488-science-fiction-future-city-planning-dubai-skyscrapers-dystopia
Social interaction	Widening inequality gap	https://www.profgalloway.com/the-great-dispersion/
	Fear/Avoidance of crowded places	https://www.nationalgeographic.com/science/2020/09/coronavirus-will-we-ever-trust-crowds-again-cvd/
	Emerging awareness of the wide range of safety and security threats	https://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/security/cybersecurity_en

ANNEX 2 – EXPLORATORY DIALOGUES BRIEFS

Exploratory dialogue 1 – September 9th, 2021 – 16:00 / 17:30

CET on Zoom

Theme: Automated vehicles

Moderator: Andrea Ricci

Speakers:

- Ghadir Pourhashem, UNIZA
- Cristina Pronello, POLITO

Indicative script

Brief introduction by moderator (10 minutes)

- Introduction to the REBALANCE project, context and objectives, originality (vs previous transport foresight exercises)
- Objectives of the exploratory dialogues and input to scenario building
- Introduction of speakers (brief bio note)
- Rules of the game

Setting the scene of the dialogue (moderator, 5 minutes: opening remarks, no immediate discussion)

Automated vehicles are expected to release people from the technical constraint of driving and allow to do multiple tasks at the same time. Is total reliance on automation a real experience of freedom?

Or is it a passive surrender leading to loss of control? If so, will the expected/alleged increase of road safety overcome/cancel out this distrust?

It is increasingly argued that driverless vehicles will only bring substantial environmental benefits if their diffusion is accompanied by a massive shift from ownership to shared mobility. Can this hinder their successful diffusion?

Can one drag the other? And what cultural shift would be needed for this to happen?

A variety of ingrained cultural and value-driven attitudes are likely to play a fundamental role in the future of AV, beyond their technological performance:

- fear of innovation
- fear of privacy breaches
- fear of losing control
- impoverishment of the human dimension of the travel experience
- ethical issues

Should policies forcefully address these factors, and nudge people towards cultural shifts that would facilitate the uptake of AVs? Or would this be a slippery slope towards the dangers of an “authoritarian state”?

Issue 1 (10 minutes)

Is it true that most technologically innovative solutions for social and environmental sustainability are in fact mostly patching problems created by previous technological

innovation (which was misdirected)? And to what extent current prevailing values (efficiency, speed, cost savings, technological progress “per se”) perpetuate this headlong flight?

Or is it possible to identify at the outset technological progress that is intrinsically conducive to sustainability?

Issue 2 (10 minutes)

How will technological progress be used/integrated?

- To increase speed and efficiency (cost, energy, time...)?
- To increase comfort, safety and quality of life?

Are these two goals compatible or are they at least partly in contrast with one another?

Will they play out in the same way for commute travel and leisure trips?

Is there a visible trend of shifting priority values behind the adoption of technological innovation and how does this translate in the case of AV?

Issue 3 (10 minutes)

Accidents and failures of self-driving vehicles: teething problems or inherent shortcomings? Moreover, what will be the significance/importance/presence of AI?

Is the fear of innovation likely to amplify/exaggerate current limitations of AV technologies and stymie their uptake? Can we learn from how fear of innovation has played out in other domains?

Issue 4 (10 minutes)

Does vehicle automation contribute to increasing societal inclusiveness? Or will it inevitably result in (further) isolation/alienation? What can we learn from the pandemics experience? And are the effects currently observed transitory or permanent?

Issue 5 (10 minutes)

Beyond purely technological aspects, what factors could hinder the adoption of new technologies?

Which are the three cultural factors that will prove most critical in the development of AV?

Recap (5 minutes)

**Exploratory dialogue 2 – September 16th, 2021 – 16:00 /
17:30 CET on Zoom**

Theme: **Digitalisation**

Moderator: Andrea Ricci

Speakers:

- Benjamin Docquir, Osborne Clarke
- Xavier Tackoen, Espaces-Mobilités

Indicative script

Brief introduction by moderator (10 minutes)

- Introduction to the REBALANCE project, context and objectives, originality (vs previous transport foresight exercises)
- Objectives of the exploratory dialogues and input to scenario building
- Introduction of speakers (brief bio note)
- Rules of the game

Setting the scene of the dialogue (moderator, 5 minutes: opening remarks, no immediate discussion)

Mobility services, whether for passengers or goods, are increasingly relying on ICT-based solutions, which are expected to increase economic efficiency, safety, and the environmental performance of the transport system, and help achieve the much-advocated goal of seamless travel. Is this a clear and unchallenged perspective or are we underestimating obstacles and undesired implications such as a loss of privacy, a decrease in social interaction opportunities, widening inequalities that leave some people behind?

Issue 1 (10 minutes): digital and green transition

Pursuing the “twin transition” has now become a widespread policy mantra.

In the transport sector, there are obvious synergies between the digital and the green dimensions, but are there also potential challenges in combining the two, and therefore the need to identify/negotiate tradeoffs?

When it comes to leveraging individual and collective motivations to promote sustainable mobility, is it potentially more effective to build upon the efficiency of digital solutions or upon environmental concerns/awareness?

Issue 2 (10 minutes) - E-life

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the grant agreement No. 101007019

Smart working, on-line shopping and other “e-life” solutions enabled by digitalization are often promoted as directly instrumental and beneficial to sustainability, including increased safety and higher economic efficiency. Some argue that this is a delusion as undesired consequences arise, for instance:

- does the ease of use brought in by digital services generate a rebound effect and boost “non-essential” mobility?
- Just-in-time practices aim at reducing “dead time” and “dead space” (with economic benefits for the industry) but increase the number of trips and of v.km
- More generally, does the digitalization of transport and new delivery patterns inevitably lead to a reduction of pax.km but an increase in ton.km?

Is there such a thing as “good vs bad efficiency”?

Issue 3 (10 minutes) - Pandemics and structural mobility changes

Pandemics have significantly changed mobility patterns, for both goods (on-line shopping) and passengers (smart working). These were enabled by digitalization. Are these changes likely to be sustained when pandemics is under control? Why or why not?

People have developed a fear of crowded spaces, but are they prepared to give up the social benefits of physical mobility? Are we heading towards an overall less convivial life?

Privacy concerns arise from the obligation to share personal data to be able to use/benefit from digital mobility services. Are people really afraid of “big brother” of, as would appear from the global spread of social networks, is it a minor evil?

Do we value efficiency more than privacy?

Issue 4 (10 minutes) Digitalisation and people-centred mobility transition

Digital-enabled solutions such as MAAS and Transport-on-Demand services, along with other ICT-based solutions such as journey-planning apps and e-ticketing are designed to better meet individual needs. Does the digital divide hinder this objective? Will it leave some groups behind (vulnerable people, elderly, technology-unsavvy, rural population...) or rather, by making it easier (and cheaper?) to move around, will it favour inclusivity? Is there a gap between public (planners, decision-makers -> more “physical”) and private (service providers -> more “virtual”) approaches?

Is access to digital mobility services being constrained by the quasi-monopolistic position of a small number of providers (e.g. GAFA)

Issue 5 (10 minutes)

Beyond purely technological aspects, what factors could hinder the adoption of digital mobility solutions?

Which are the three cultural factors that will prove most critical in the successful development of digital-enabled mobility?

Recap (5 minutes)

Exploratory dialogue 3– September 23rd, 2021 – 16:00 / 17:30

CET on Zoom

Theme: Towards greener transport choices

Moderator: Andrea Ricci

Speakers:

- Andreu Ulled, ERSILIA
- Robert Braun, IHS

Rough script

Brief introduction by moderator (10 minutes)

- Introduction to the REBALANCE project, context and objectives, originality (vs previous transport foresight exercises)
- Objectives of the exploratory dialogues and input to scenario building
- Introduction of speakers (brief bio note)
- Rules of the game

Setting the scene of the dialogue (moderator, 5 minutes: opening remarks, no immediate discussion)

Signs towards **greener transport choices** are emerging in Europe.

Industry is making cleaner vehicles increasingly available and performant (electromobility, cleaner fuels)

Government plays an important role through standards, taxation, phasing out, but also, at the local level, through the redesign of urban, greener spaces and infrastructure

But can this basket of opportunities be effective in realizing a green mobility transition without a major shift in the attitude of citizens and mobility users?

Or – more bluntly - can we say that government and industry moves are in fact primarily pushed forward by a changing societal attitude towards environment protection and the pursuance of a healthier life?

Issue 1 (10 minutes) – Environmental and health concerns

Are environmental and health concerns playing a real role in fostering modal shifts?

Are people really driven by knowledge and evidence on the social and environmental benefits of green choices, or is it rather the need/obligation to fulfil social norms that drives them?

Will initiatives like “Fridays for Future” really make a difference in the medium-long term? And if so, does this contribute to underline intergenerational differences in awareness and motivation?

Cultural changes take time, but they (are expected to) bring changes that are structural. Will demand-side policies - such as access regulations, infrastructure charging, standards – be no longer necessary once a new mobility culture prevails?

Issue 2 (10 minutes) – Active travel

The shift towards “active travel” is a major component of the green transition. Active travel is usually defined as travel that requires physical activity (walking, cycling etc.), generating social benefits in both environmental and health terms. How deep are the changes in values and attitudes that are required to enact a visible move to active travel?

On the other hand, travel choices can be influenced by the extent to which the traveler is allowed to be “the actor”, making all decisions (direction, speed, stops, changes of plan etc.). In that case it is private cars that allow maximum “agency” and control...

How is the advent of micromobility changing the scene? Is it a substitute for private, or is it – more worryingly – also a substitute for physically active modes (walking and cycling)? Or does it cover a (new) transitional zone between both modes?

Issue 3 (10 minutes) - Pandemics and structural mobility changes

To what extent is the pandemics crisis likely to yield structural behavioural changes (a “new normal” where substantial modal shifts become permanent)? Or is it bound to be reabsorbed once the immediate health concerns are (perceived to be) overcome?

A case in point: the role of air travel after covid-19:

- Rising awareness of its ecological footprint vs. revitalisation of leisure travel
- Business travels vs Zoom meetings
- Ban of domestic flights where an alternative train route exists
- Night trains back in fashion?

Issue 4 (10 minutes) – Gender issues

Is gender a meaningful variable in the transition to greener mobility?

If so, does this have to do with gender-specific value differences?

Issue 5 (10 minutes) -

Beyond purely technological aspects, what factors could hinder the transition towards greener transport?

Which are the three cultural factors that will prove most critical in the transition?

Recap (5 minutes)

Exploratory dialogue 4– September 30th, 2021 – 16:00 / 17:30

CET on Zoom

Theme: The future role of the car

Moderator: Andrea Ricci

Speakers:

- Jens Schade - TUD
- Stefan Gössling - Lund University

Rough script

Brief introduction by moderator (5 minutes)

- Introduction to the REBALANCE project, context and objectives, originality (vs previous transport foresight exercises)
- Objectives of the exploratory dialogues and input to scenario building
- Introduction of speakers (brief bio note)
- Rules of the game

Setting the scene of the dialogue (moderator, 5 minutes: opening remarks, no immediate discussion)

Private car use is recognized as having significant negative impacts on environment, health, and safety. It generates congestion, consumes significant urban space and affects quality of life in general.

Access regulation, initiatives to foster active mobility and micromobility, and to make public transport more attractive address some of these concerns.

But private car ownership and use is deeply ingrained in our culture, and car sales keep growing.

Is a radical shift away from cars a realistic perspective? And which “key values” should be promoted to achieve it?

Issue 1 (10 minutes) – Freedom

Driving a car is perceived as an expression of freedom: the driver is “in control”, can decide where, when, at what speed, and with what itinerary to move around.

But is this not a delusion, when suffering frustrating congestion, time losses to find parking spots, impotence in avoiding accidents provoked by others, along with high economic costs?

Is “agency” a fundamental determinant of mobility choices? Could more and better evidence of real costs and benefits, both individual and collective, help deconstructing the current paradigm, and convincing people that their real need is to move, not to drive?

Issue 2 (10 minutes) – car ownership

It is often argued that the main reason behind the prevalence of private car use is the “status symbol” notion attached to the car, and the subsequent reticence to give up ownership.

The emergence of shared vehicles and shared rides schemes can be optimistically interpreted as a promising signal in this regard. But will it become prevalent? And which “soft spots” in people’s values and perception must be addressed for this to happen?

On the other hand, if it is sustained, the generalized acceptance of shared schemes could lead car use to become an integral part of more sustainable, multimodal and seamless mobility patterns. This would then further rule out any perspective of phasing out cars as such! Ultimately, will a radical shift to shared schemes be enough to curb the dramatic impacts of automobility?

Issue 3 (10 minutes) – Technology

Technological innovation is mostly presented as a promising pathway towards sustainability: cleaner propulsion, vehicle automation, “smart”, ICT-based mobility can undoubtedly bring - if only incremental - improvements in environmental and safety-related performances of transport systems and services.

But is this ultimately decisive? Or is it not a further step towards the consolidation of the car-based mobility culture, one that in the end definitively precludes a radical shift away from automobility?

And even worse, could technological progress generate perverse rebound effects which would ultimately mainly serve the interests of the automotive industry rather than those of society?

Question 4 (10 minutes) – Pandemics

What was observed, only a few years ago, as a progressive disenchantment with car ownership and use, especially among the young, seem to be now at least partially offset by the urge to avoid crowded transport solutions.

To minimize contact with others, many people are choosing to travel in their own vehicles. Since the outbreak of COVID-19 the use of public transportation and carpools has declined significantly worldwide.

Are COVID-related concerns an alibi to sticking to private car use, where all collective modes, but also shared cars, are perceived as a health risk?

Question 5 (10 minutes)

Beyond purely technological aspects, which are the three cultural factors that will prove most critical in shaping the future of cars?

Recap (5 minutes)

Exploratory dialogue 5– November 11th, 16 :00 / 17:30 CET on Zoom

Theme: Living, working and shopping patterns

Moderator: Andrea Ricci

Speakers:

- Alain L'Hostis- Université Gustave Eiffel
- Cristina Marolda,

Indicative script

Brief introduction by moderator (5 minutes)

- Introduction to the REBALANCE project, context and objectives, originality (vs previous transport foresight exercises)
- Objectives of the exploratory dialogues and input to scenario building
- Introduction of speakers (brief bio note)
- Rules of the game

Setting the scene of the dialogue (moderator, 5 minutes: opening remarks, no immediate discussion)

Living, working and shopping patterns are changing in Europe and transforming our urban context.

As ICT-based technology permeates our life, the so-called "smart" solutions become the default option for many people, supposedly bringing time savings and overall efficiency gains.

Pandemics has certainly accelerated/exacerbated this change, but a more structural trend was visible even before, which technological innovation alone cannot explain.

The implications are far-reaching, they affect urban form, infrastructure requirements, and most importantly basic values such as equality of opportunities

Issue 1 (10 minutes) – urban "model"

Which "model" are the aspirations of the majority of citizens – and specifically of young generations - aligned with?

- Suburban dwelling, quiet, more indoor and outdoor space
- Inner city dwelling, "where the action is"
- Rural escape, return to nature
- 15-minute city, multi-nodal city

Are there any robust change factors that can help predict which of these will be favored in the long term?

Issue 2 (10 minutes) – Comfort vs convenience

Efficiency, in the guise of “individual convenience”, appears to be the main driver of changing patterns.

To what extent is efficiency pursued at the expense of other fundamental values and aspirations, both at the individual level (comfort) and more importantly at the overall community level (equity, conviviality)?

Issue 3 (10 minutes) – value of time

Awareness of mobility injustice is a growing.

Long commuting times, in particular, reflect differently on different-economic groups, and attention is growing on “kinetic elites” and other inequality risks.

Urban density has been systematically equated with efficiency (quicker accessibility).

Is urban sprawl the undisputed culprit? Should the density dogma be revisited?

Can polycentric cities help reducing mobility injustice?

Issue 4 (10 minutes) – value of space

The massive shift towards remote activities (work, learn, shop etc.) entails that the availability of individual space becomes a prominent concern. Which of these two extreme alternatives is more likely to prevail?

- Alternative 1: the shift towards remote, virtual life is here to stay. It is therefore necessary to redesign our space and the logistics available in order to ensure comfort and efficiency in the medium/long-term. The real estate market undergoes a major structural change, with residential space in higher demand while office space loses value.
- Alternative 2: confinements and lockdowns have shown that the social/convivial dimensions of most our activities are essential to ensure an acceptable quality of life. Remote work and education are limited to the essential and a majority of people/families are content with marginal readjusting of their available space

Will urban expansion drive the evolution of transport infrastructure and mobility services, or the other way around?

Issue 5 (10 minutes)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the grant agreement No. 101007019

Beyond purely technological aspects, which are the three cultural factors that will prove most critical in determining future patterns of living, working and shopping?

Recap (5 minutes)

